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The Nexus Between Globalization, Drug Trafficking and National Security: A Comprehensive Study

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Abstract

The issue at hand is the impact of globalisation on the rise of drug trafficking networks and their affects on national security, The Illicit trafficking of drugs has drastically increased because of globalization and a free global market, not only in India but all over the world and the transnational nature of trafficking presents challenges to law enforcement. The emerging new trends make it difficult for law enforcement agencies to investigate and enforce the law. This increase in drug trafficking is leading to a threat to national security

This research work explores the complex interconnection of globalization, drug trafficking, and national security, with special reference to India. As it increases interconnectivity and blurs conventional boundaries, globalization has also facilitated the dissemination of transnational organized crimes, such as the illegal drug trade. Geographically located between the Golden Crescent and Golden Triangle—two of the world's largest opium-producing areas—India has come to play a more prominent role as a transit hub for drug trafficking, which carries serious socio-economic and security concerns.

This Paper discusses how liberalization of the market, advances in technology, and freer movement of goods and people have made it easier for international networks of drug trafficking to expand. It also explains how globalization has exposed national security to threats such as the emergence of narco-terrorism and exploitation of drug trafficking routes by terrorist groups. The research also points to the challenges confronting law enforcement authorities in dealing with the constantly changing techniques of trafficking, particularly in the wake of the dark net, cryptocurrencies, and global courier networks.

In a nutshell, the article underlines the compelling need for a concerted world strategy to balance the escalating danger of drug smuggling during the era of globalization and identifies the fact that national security cannot be guaranteed unless the transnational nature of this crime is challenged.

Keywords: Drug Trafficking; Globalisation; Organized Crime; National Security

1. Introduction

Lord Buddha in his scriptures provided 5 precepts as guidelines for an ethical and moral life, these guidelines say that people should refrain from violence (which can be inferred from the first four principles) and refrain from intoxicants (inferred from 5th precept). Our historical figures Mahatma Gandhi, Sant Tukaram, Sant Kabir and Vinoba Bhave were advocates of Non-Violence. The first prime minister of Independent India Jawaharlal Nehru was also a strong advocate of peace. India the land of Lord Buddha, Mahatma Gandhi, Jawaharlal Nehru and so on is growing into a violent society.

Anthony McGrew defined Globalization as a concept which refers to the widening, deepening, and acceleration of worldwide connectivity or interconnectedness ¹ . Globalization integrates the world's economies, politics and cultures (Adam Volle, 2023)². Globalization has dissolved the borders of countries by bringing in a unified world system (Wallerstein 1947). Globalization is giving rise to crimes and terrorism which are converting into a global phenomenon from a regional one. Drug Trafficking is also a crime which is becoming a global phenomenon and a transnational crime due to globalization. The availability of an open market, faster transport and a free and wide communication range is raising opportunities to traffic drugs and poverty which was brought in due to free market capitalism is also a reason why people are trying to illegally sell drugs.

“India being located between two major opium-producing regions; the Golden Crescent (Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Iran) and the Golden Triangle (Myanmar, Thailand, and Laos) has become a centre for the transit and trafficking of drugs.”³ Over the last two decades, there has been a substantial increase in the illicit trade(trafficking) of Drugs and as a

¹ Baylis, John, Steve Smith, and Patricia Owens, eds. 2020. *The Globalization of World Politics*. 8th ed. London, England: Oxford University Press

² Volle, Adam. "globalization". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 29 Nov. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/money/topic/globalization>. Accessed 29 December 2023.

³ Global Organized Crime Index, <https://ocindex.net/country/india>

consequence, trends in trafficking have been evolving.⁴

As the illicit trade is increasing consequently there is an increase in threat to national security, these drug trafficking routes can be used by terrorists, and weapons trafficking will also increase as both are interconnected and they are organized crimes, money laundering, human trafficking and many other crimes will also increase as they are interconnected and even if they are not interconnected the networks used by drug trafficking can also be used by other transnational and global crimes. In this way, there is a nexus between globalisation Drugs and National security.

2. Globalization and Increased Crime Rate

Globalization is defined by various authors in different ways, Anthony McGrew defined Globalization as a concept which refers to the widening, deepening, and acceleration of worldwide connectivity or interconnectedness⁵. Globalization integrates the world's economies, politics and cultures (Adam Volle, 2023)⁶. Globalization has dissolved the borders of countries by bringing in a unified world system (Wallerstein 1947).

What globalization basically means is that the entire world becomes one global system or village and opens up for free trade, cultural exchange, knowledge, technology and exchange of various other things with one and other countries. This is achieved by making laws and policies of the country liberal to facilitate trade and travelling.

2.1 Increased Crime Rate

Although Globalization results in many positive things like the exchange of advanced technology and trade of goods and economics, we know that everything has drawbacks and

⁴ Narcotics Control Bureau Annual Report 2021

⁵ Baylis, John, Steve Smith, and Patricia Owens, eds. 2020. *The Globalization of World Politics*. 8th ed. London, England: Oxford University Press.

⁶ Volle, Adam. "globalization". *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, 29 Nov. 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/money/topic/globalization>. Accessed 29 December 2023.

in the same way globalization also has its drawbacks and one of its drawbacks is the increased crime rate.

Globalization creates new and exciting opportunities not only for businessmen and traders but also for criminals. These criminals form groups and alliances and commit organised transnational crimes, they also use their power to criminalize politics, business, police, trade, etc.

Crime Increases due to various reasons like open market, liberal policies, and fast transport. Due to the opportunities given by open markets criminals can freely communicate and transport, moreover, global banking systems are facilitating the movement of money across countries and making it easier for criminals to do all sorts of crimes and money laundering. Sometimes people commit crimes because of their financial status, free market capitalism has brought poverty to many countries and committing crimes and selling drugs is a tempting way to make money and to make ends meet in a poor household.

3. State of Drug Trafficking In India

According to The Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances Act of 1988 (NDPS Act), illicit traffic means—Cultivation of or gathering of poppy, coca and cannabis; engaging in the production, manufacture, possession, sale, Purchase, Transportation, warehousing, concealment, use or consumption, import inter-state, export inter-state, import in India, export from India or transshipment, of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances; dealing in any activities related to Narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances without having licence and in addition to that harbouring persons engaged in any of the aforementioned activities is illicit trafficking.⁷

3.1 Historical Overview and Drug Scene in India

⁷ The Prevention of Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances Act, 1988, § 2(e), No.46, Acts of Parliament, 1988 (India)

There is a very long relationship between mankind and drugs, the use of drugs is as old as the history of mankind. Almost all primitive and modern societies have used one or the other kind of drug for various purposes.⁸ India has been and is a traditional producer of drugs. However, opium cultivation boomed in India during the period of British rule. British were fascinated by tea and they were the largest consumers of tea, in exchange for tea, the British cultivated opium in Bihar, Bengal and the North-Eastern states of India in order to illegally export opium to China and in return they got tea.⁹ Eventually, other states of India started cultivating drugs and the local mafia started getting involved in the drug trafficking systems which led to the creation of a power vacuum.¹⁰

After the Britishers left the new legislation criminalised drug trafficking and drug usage but the widespread poverty paved the way for illegal cultivation and trafficking. Also, India being located between internationally acknowledged two major opium-producing regions; towards the west Golden Crescent (Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Iran)¹¹ and the east Golden Triangle (Myanmar, Thailand, and Laos)¹² has become a centre for the transit and illicit trafficking of drugs.¹³

The two-way illegal flow of these drugs and chemicals not only violates India's borders, but also poses a significant threat to national security.

India is recognized as an important drug-producing nation internationally (Paul and Rao, 2002). With an increase in profit, new traffickers appeared in marginalized sections of

⁸ Dr. Janaki MC, Drug Trafficking- A Analytical Study, 5, Indian Social Science Journal.

https://www.academia.edu/32092921/DRUG_TRAFFICKING_A_ANALYTICAL_STUDY

⁹ Sradha J, Abdul Razak A S, Suranya S Kumar, Biju Antony, Drug Trafficking in India, 4, International Journal of Research Publications and Reviews. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374163245_Drug_Trafficking_in_India

¹⁰ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374163245_Drug_Trafficking_in_India

¹¹ Golden Crescent is a mountainous area of Iran, Afghanistan and Pakistan, it is the largest illicit drug supplier all over the world. Golden Crescent supplies drugs to India through these three routes: the Balkan route, the Northern route and the Southern route. Most of the heroin enters India through these routes from Afghanistan.

¹² Golden Triangle is the mountain area of Burma, Laos and Thailand. Most of the Drugs produced in this region are transhipped to international markets only a small quantity of various opiates are illegally trafficked to India.

¹³ Global Organized Crime Index, <https://ocindex.net/country/india>

society.¹⁴ Drug trafficking has become a coping mechanism for poor urban dwellers. Though there are laws preventing drug trafficking it is hard to considerably reduce it because drug trafficking being an organized crime makes it hard for law enforcement agencies to catch the real offenders or criminals and the victims do not cooperate and the investigators should be sensitive while dealing with victims leading to difficulty in finding the offender.

3.2 Evolution of Trends and Routes

Globalization has led to the emergence of new routes for trafficking and also new markets for the sale of these goods, In India according to NCORD, 70% of them are trafficked by using land routes, by which we can understand that most of the trafficking happens between cross-border alliances. There are sea and air routes too, The east and west coasts of India are major transits for drug trafficking, and drugs are trafficked using small fishing boats. Through personal carriers and postal services, drugs are trafficked through air routes. Along with these routes, there are many new routes which are used by traffickers, these routes, trends and patterns will always be changing as technology changes and with the facilitation of globalization. Nowadays sea routes are being used popularly as it is hard to catch the criminals who are using sea routes also due to the increase in online shopping websites drugs are being trafficked by couriers, and like this new trends will emerge every day.

As per the report posted by the Ministry of Home Affairs on 14 December 2022, In the year 2021, 78331 cases were registered under the NDPS Act, whereas in 2017 the number of cases registered was 63800, there is an increase of 22.8% in the registered cases over the span of 5 years. In 2020 the cases registered were considerably less compared to 2019 and

¹⁴ Rahul Jain, Illegal drug trafficking in India and its future, file:///C:/Users/lohit/OneDrive/Desktop/crimes/Illegal%20drug%20trafficking%20in%20India%20and%20it's%20future%20_%20Rahul%20Jain%20-%20Academia.edu.html

2021 because of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the traffickers adopted new trends and routes to traffic during the pandemic. The number of cases registered in 2020 was 59806 and in 2021, 78331 cases were registered by this we can deduce that the traffickers have adopted new trends and routes to illegally trade the drugs. It is very clear that there is a consistent growth in illicit trafficking over the past few years, in addition to this drug trafficking is diverted to somewhere else when the government clears out one place.¹⁵

3.3 Consequences of Drug Trafficking

The consequences of Drug trafficking are widespread, drugs cause physical and mental damage to drug abusers and as well to the people who are closely related to the drug abusers, because drug abuse negatively impacts the abusers' family's mental status, social status, etc. If the parents are drug addicts it might result in poor mental health of children and sometimes the children might become criminals because of their parents. Drugs impact health and lead to sickness and diseases, there might also be cases of deaths caused by overdoses, If a parent overdoses their children will become orphans, and if a youngster overdoses there is a decrease in national productivity. There are many cases of Induced or injected drug users, and they share uncleaned needles leading to many diseases like HIV, Hep-b, Hep-c, Septicemia and etc. People commit crimes for drug money, there is an increase in homicides due to drugs and also an increase in premature mortality((U) *Impact of Drugs on Society - National Drug Threat Assessment 2010 (UNCLASSIFIED)*). Resources used for public needs are traded off to overcome the damage caused by drug trafficking. All these are indirectly linked to a reduction in national productivity.¹⁶

¹⁵ Dr. Janaki MC, Drug Trafficking- A Analytical Study, 5, Indian Social Science Journal.
https://www.academia.edu/32092921/DRUG_TRAFFICKING_A_ANALYTICAL_STUDY

¹⁶ (U) Impact of Drugs on Society - National Drug Threat Assessment 2010 (UNCLASSIFIED) (no date).
<https://www.justice.gov/archive/ndic/pubs38/38661/drugImpact.htm>.

4. Globalization of Drug Trafficking and National Security

Drug Trafficking is a global problem that affects all countries, as we know globalization means that it is easy for international trade and communication, and access to these telecommunications and technologies facilitated criminal activities to expand into international markets¹⁷. Globalization facilitated terrorism and criminal activities through the movement of people. International Civil aviation made hijacking easy and possible (Ahmad and Mwanza, 2006). Television provides info about the world, technology provides a wide range of weapons which are being traded and illegally trafficked through the drug trafficking routes.

the explosives used in the 1993 Mumbai terrorist attacks were smuggled into India using the same routes through which drugs and other contraband items were trafficked by the Dawood gang

Trade barriers are reduced, because of which people and goods can easily move. Open borders made it easy for people to transport and distribute drugs. The development of mobiles and technology and the internet led to new crimes that are cybercrime and cyber espionage, the Internet is being used as space for selling drugs illegally, and transfer of money is happening in crypto currency, bitcoin, etc making it hard for law agencies to find the trafficker. Globalization led to the capitalisation of the market and this led to poverty and unemployment as a consequence pushed the poor to engage in illicit trade activities (UNESCO, 1999, 5)

Globalization is a major factor which acted as a driving force for the decline in the intermediation margin which led to a decrease in the price of drugs¹⁸, every market depends on demand, supply and price, as price decreased there was a rise in demand. Demand

¹⁷ Ahmad, U. and Mwanza, J. (2006) 'Globalisation and crime,' *ResearchGate* [Preprint]. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228381107_Globalisation_and_crime.

¹⁸ Read: Storti, C. and De Grauwe, P. (2009) 'Globalization and the price decline of illicit drugs,' *International Journal of Drug Policy*, 20(1), pp. 48–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2007.11.016>.

increases and as well as illicit traffic is also increasing. This illicit traffic fueled violence, crime and corruption.

The Profit that the drug traffickers is so high that they use it to get access to high-level governments and military officials, and the profit is also being used as funding by terrorists to move from one place to another. Funding for terrorism is taken from trafficking, credit card fraud, money laundering and much more, all this money is helping terrorists travel the world and get access to new equipment and weapons and eventually helping them pose threats to the nations. Terrorists use drug trafficking networks, and they also sell drugs to fund terrorism which is called Narco-terrorism. They join hands with drug lords¹⁹ to facilitate narco-terrorism. Terrorists give protection to drug dealers with arms and in return, drug traffickers assist the terrorists to do cross-border activities and to move from one nation to another.

Pakistan frequently used Narco terrorism as a weapon to create trouble in border states of India, there were several instances where drugs were seized from military men in Kashmir. NIA spokesperson revealed that Some of the drug traffickers are generating funds for terrorist groups like Lasker-E-Taiyba and Hizb-ul-Mujahidin. Nowadays Narco-military is also being emerged as a challenge in J&K (DGP Dilbagh Singh).²⁰ Not only Jammu and Kashmir but many other border states like Manipur, Mizoram, Punjab and Rajasthan are affected due to Narco-Terrorism.

5. Faced by Law Enforcement agencies and Challenges Recommendations

The trends in trafficking keep evolving as a result the challenges posed by law enforcement agencies become greater, and law enforcement agencies lack training, experience and resources to investigate the new trends of trafficking.²¹ Law enforcement should be aware

¹⁹ Oxford dictionary meaning of drug lord is a powerful leader of a group of people who buy and sell large quantities of illegal drugs

²⁰ Narula, P. (2022) *Priyanka Narula*. <https://www.claws.in/narco-terrorism-in-jk-an-emerging-security-threat/>.

²¹ United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, <https://www.unodc.org/e4j/en/tip-and-som/module-9/key-issues/challenges-to-an-effective-criminal-justice-response.html>

of these new emerging trends to confront the challenges faced by them.

The Illicit trafficking of drugs has drastically increased not only in India but all over the world and the transnational nature of trafficking presents challenges to law enforcement. The emerging new trends make it difficult for law enforcement agencies to investigate and enforce the law as there is a lack of cooperation from the victims as well as witnesses and informers, the need for new resources is more as trends are emerging.²² When there is cross-border criminal activity there are operational difficulties and there are differences in laws between the countries as a result there is complexity in investigating and prosecuting the offenders.²³ So there should be cooperation between the countries to overcome this, they have to make some agreements to combat drug trafficking and they have to interact about the trafficking and discuss ways to reduce it.

As there is an increase in usage of technology the offenders are using the dark net to sell drugs and it is difficult to trace the seller because of anonymity. The transactions are in Cryptocurrency, bitcoin etc making them harder to trace and they are delivering drugs through couriers by putting them in boxes which have logos of E-commerce companies and websites. Traffickers keep on changing their routes which makes it harder for law enforcement agencies to catch them. Even if the police catch the offender, it is hard to prove that the suspect is a convict because of the transnational nature of the crime.

As we discussed before drug trafficking is an organised crime it has different layers in its network so it is hard to catch the offender, sometimes the victim is considered an offender. There is no law governing organized crime, Criminal Conspiracy Section 120-A of IPC is the only law-related grouped crime in this kind of act, and so there is a need for comprehensive law to control organised crime.

According to NCORD, 70% of them are trafficked by using land routes, by which we can understand that most of the trafficking happens between cross-border alliances, which

²² Ketan Patil, Astha Pandey, Drug Trafficking: A Growing Problem in India, 39 (2022)

²³ <https://www.unodc.org/e4j/en/tip-and-som/module-9/key-issues/challenges-to-an-effective-criminal-justice-response.html>

means there is a need for stringent security in borders and check posts and measures should be taken to control cross-border trafficking. And despite all these measures the demand should be reduced which can be done by spreading awareness.

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(U) *Impact of Drugs on Society - National Drug Threat Assessment 2010*
(UNCLASSIFIED) (no date).

<https://www.justice.gov/archive/ndic/pubs38/38661/drugImpact.htm>.

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